

Human Capital Management and Organizational Performance in United Bank for Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State

Author's Details:

Abaikpa, Udeme Anthony

Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Management Sciences
Akwa Ibom State University, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria
udemeabaiakpa@gmail.com
+234-08063787705

Thomas, Cornelia David

Department of Management, Faculty of Social and Management Sciences
Ritman University, Ikot Ekpene, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
thomas.cornelia@ritmanuniversity.edu.ng
+234-9098345556

Dr. Udom Sunday Daniel

Department of Business Administration & Management, Faculty of Management Sciences
Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
awesomeblisscharis@gmail.com
+2348038750959

Emmanuel, Okon Etuk

Department of Business Administration & Management, Faculty of Management Sciences
Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
dmautocompanyltd@gmail.com
+2347030553700

Abstract

The study was designed to examine the relationship between human capital management and organizational performance in United Bank for Africa Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. To achieve this objective, survey research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study consisted of management staff, senior staff and junior staff of the United Bank for Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State which is made up of 82 staff with sample size of 68 staff. The study utilized Taro Yamane Scientific technique. The instrument used for data collection was Human Capital Management and Organizational Performance Questionnaire (HCMOPQ). Tables, Mean, Standard Deviation and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient were adopted as analytical tools for this study. Two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The result of the study showed that there was a positive significant relationship between human capital management and organizational performance in United Bank for Africa Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. The result of the findings also revealed that organizational performance is dependent on the extent of its staff training and timely appraisal of employees. This implies that increased investment in staff training and timely appraisal of employees by the bank would yield greater returns in organizational performance.

Keywords: Human capital management, training, performance appraisal, performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

The role of human capital management in achievement of organizational performance, particularly in banking industry cannot be ignored. This is because human capital is considered as one of the core components of intellectual capital in any organization. Human capital and knowledge-based managements are emerging as the key to wealth creation. Organizations have various aspects of resources, financial, physical, and human resources. Of all the assets of the organization, the human capital is the most critical. Organizational goals and objectives might be a mirage (i.e left only on papers or drawing boards) without the proper management of this all-important resource called human capital. All other assets are inanimate; it is the human capital (employees) that breathe life into them. However, the management and practice of human capital should become an important factor in any organization because they impact on the

behavior, response and action of the employees which consequently, affect the performance of the organization and achievement of its goals and objectives. According to Wurim (2012) where human capital is not well managed, organizations will be confronted with the problems of over or under staffing, inability to attract and retain the people required and difficulty in the development and training of highly talented personnel.

Apparently, human capital unarguably constitutes most critical and fundamental issue in the management of both public and private organizations. Perhaps, this aspect of management has elicited more researches, seminars, and workshops than any other area recently. This underscores the centrality of, and the need for proper management of the human component of organizations for the realization of planned goals. Human capital management's cardinal aim therefore, is to generate strategic capability by ensuring that the organization has the skilled, committed and well-trained employees it needs to sustain competitive advantage (Armstrong, 2012). Consequently, it is not enough for organizations, for instance, banks to hire and promote the brightest individuals they could find. They should nurture and support them into developing and sharing their potentials through training. This is because an organization that has trained, skilled and creative employees can easily avoid wasteful investment and improve its performance as well as its profitability. Therefore, improving the quality and relevance of human capital management would enable organizations to better understand and appraise their overall people-related strengths and weaknesses and identify areas for improvement.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The management of people has developed over time spanning from the era of industrial relations, personnel management and recently, human capital management. An effective human capital management is a key factor for optimum organizational performance, growth and sustainable development. However, it is not enough for organizations to hire, develop and promote the brightest individuals they could find. They should nurture and support them into developing and sharing their potentials through effective training. This is because an organization that lacks trained, skilled and creative employees can hardly improve its performance and avoid wasteful investment, (Armstrong, 2012). Therefore, improving the quality and relevance of human capital management may help organizations to better understand and appraise their overall people-related strengths and weaknesses and identify areas for improvement. But several extant literature reveal that, human capital management is faced with a lot of challenges ranging from poor training methods, poor performance appraisal and reward systems that can help organizations achieve their desired objectives and goals (Roberts, 2020). It is against this background that, this study is designed to examine the relationship between human capital management and organizational performance in United Bank for Africa Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to examine the relationship between human capital management and organizational performance in United Bank for Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Specific objectives include:

- i. To examine the relationship between staff training and organizational performance in United Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. To evaluate the relationship between staff performance appraisal and organizational performance in United Bank for Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

- i. What has been the relationship between staff training and organizational performance in United Bank for Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State?
- ii. What is the relationship between staff performance appraisal and organizational performance in United Bank for Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State?

1.5 Hypotheses

From the objectives of the study, the following hypotheses were formulated for this study:

- i. Training has no significant relationship with organizational performance in United Bank for Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. Staff performance appraisal has no significant relationship with organizational performance in United Bank for Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Concept of Human Capital Management

The world over, human capital is considered one of the core components of intellectual capital and is a critical resource in many organizations today. Proper management of this all-important resource is imperative. Human capital management a set of practices related to people resource management e.g. workforce acquisition, workforce management and workforce optimization (Armstrong, 2009). Purcell (2010) defines human capital management as a strategy or an approach to making decisions on the intentions and plans of the organization concerning the relationship and its recruitment, training, development, performance management, reward and employee relations strategies, policies and practices. Human capital management is concerned with purposeful measurement, not just measurement. The defining characteristics of human capital management is the use of metrics to guide an approach to managing people that regards them as assets and emphasizes that competitive advantage is achieved by strategic investments in those assets through employee engagement and retention, talent management and learning and development program (Armstrong, 2009). He opines that human capital management provides a bridge between human resource and business strategy. But Kearns (2009) views human capital management as the total development of human potential expressed as organizational value.

Human capital represents the individual stock of knowledge embedded in the firm's collective capability to extract the best solutions from its individual employees (Bontis, 2009). Edvinson and Malone, (2010) view human capital as the sum of the workers' skills, experience, capabilities, and tacit knowledge. Davenport and Prusac, (2010) add that human capital includes the intangible resources of abilities, effort, and time that workers bring to invest in their work. Evidently, human capital involves investment in education, training, skills, health, and other values that cannot be separated from the individual. In the words of Marimuthu *et al* (2009), human capital simply refers to the processes that relate to training, education and other professional initiatives in order to increase the levels of knowledge, skills, abilities, values, and social assets of an employee which will lead to the employee's job satisfaction and performance.

Apparently, investment on employee's education, skills, values etc. all enhance job satisfaction and performance with less job turn over in the organization. All organizations depend on its employees to succeed. Through human capital management, commitment to duty is enhanced and hence the stress on investment in education and training in the workplace is reduced. Organization for economic Co-operation and Development (OECD 2011) defines human capital as the knowledge, skills, competencies, abilities, and other attributes embodied in individuals that facilitate the creation of personal, social and economic wellbeing. Several extant literature emphasize the need for training of human capital as a key management tool for organizational success in the contemporary world of competition. However, organizations that de-emphasize or lays no premium on the training and development of its human capital are bound to fail or tilting toward a state of collapse.

2.1.2 Staff Training

Training is one of the crucial areas of human capital management. Training constitutes the pivot in which organizational survival is run. Training is the method of developing employees' cognitive and psychomotor skills towards enhancing his productivity (Ezeani & Oladele, 2013). Training has been recognized as one of managerial tools that enhance job satisfaction globally. According to Atif, *et al*, (2011), training is, basically, a practical education through which knowledge and skills are developed, experience and inefficiencies are overcome and closer approximation can be achieved. Sajuyigbe and Amusat, (2012) believe that training and development enhance employees' personal job satisfaction. According to Raja *et al* (2011) training and development is a very important tool used by organizations to compete in this competitive and changing world. Similarly, Vichet (2009) opines that in facing fierce competition and ever rapidly changing market environments, organizations must improve productivity, efficiency, customer service, staff retention through training and development of their employees.

Human capital is the basis of all resources and it is the indispensable means of converting other resources to man kind's use and benefits. So how well we train and develop human capital is fundamental in deciding how much we will accomplish as an organization, (Comma, 2008). According to (Devi & Shaik, 2012) training helps to develop employees to the fullest advantage in order to enhance their organizational performance. According to (Irene, 2013), the central role of staff training has long been recognized by many organizations. Training both physically, socially, intellectually and mentally are very essential in facilitating not only the level of productivity but also the development of personnel in any organization, (Olusanya *et al*, 2012). According to (Bakare, 2012) training is the systematic development of the knowledge, skills, and attitudes required by a person in order to effectively perform a given task or job. He further describes training process as one of the most pervasive methods for enhancing the performance of individuals and communicating organizational goals to personnel. This implies that within every organization, training occurs at all levels of personnel, and trainees may vary in terms of age, work experience, disability, educational background, ethnic origin, and skill level. Thus, training is the best solution to improve employee's understanding and let them know how to use their specific skills to enhance organizational performance (Muhammad, 2012).

Inyang and Akpama (2002) view training as one of the core human capital management programs which is directed towards the acquisition of specific knowledge and skills for the purpose of an occupation or task. Training could be in-service training or on – the - job training, where the worker is attached to an officer of supervisory level to assist improve the new officer to improve their performance. Training is necessary because of changes in technology and new methods for the improvement of the overall performance of the organization. Human capital management literature identifies and provides several newer approaches to training employees. Skills, knowledge and abilities can be imparted through the use of new technologies and adapting to innovative training methods including program instructions (PI), computer and simulated games, role playing and audio-visual tools are more effective and therefore same are being extensively used in current training curriculums. These newer techniques combined with the traditional methods such as mentoring, coaching, lectures, conferences, movie or films and case studies represent effective means of training in organizations (Irene, 2009; Armstrong, 2010).

Stoner (2002) opines that training has a distinct role in the achievement of an organizational goal by incorporating the interests of organization and the workforce. In today's organizations, training becomes the most important factor because it increases the efficiency and the effectiveness of both employees and the organization. Training helps to ensure that organizational members possess the knowledge and skills they need to perform their jobs effectively, take on new responsibilities and adapt to changing conditions (Jones, George and Hill, 2000). According to (Okanya, 2008), training need occurs when there is a shortfall in overall performance of organization. However, behavior modification which according to Armstrong (2010) must be the outcome of training program to organizational performance. Consequently, organizations work with variety of staff members not only for improvement connected with staff members but with organization's effectiveness as well. Khandekar and Sharma (2003) opine that an organization that invests in training of its staff is likely to gain a sustainable advantage and enjoy superior performance.

2.1.3 Staff Performance Appraisal and Organizational Performance

Performance appraisal is one of the most significant aspects of human capital management activities designed and performed in the organizations as well as in every walk of life. According to Meysam, Mohammad, Behrooz & Ebrahim (2012), performance appraisal can be viewed as an act of testing, evaluating, measuring and justifying the performance displayed by the employees during a specific period of time. The term performance appraisal are sometimes called performance review, employee appraisal, performance evaluation, employee evaluation, employee rating, merit evaluation, or personnel rating. The objective of performance appraisal is to maintain the performance of the employees up to desired levels, by motivating employees who depend on the workplace environment and rules and regulations at work (Tassew, 2010).

Performance appraisal helps to identify and overcome the problems faced by the employees on their work (Mackey and Johnson, 2000). Although it has many benefits for the organization, performance appraisal also has the equal probability of having a bad impact on the organization as well

as on employee performance, (Rudman 2008). This implies that performance appraisal can improve the work performance and employee satisfaction and as well demotivate employees and leave a bad impression on them. According to Brown, (2010) most of the employees do not approve a continuous performance appraisal; they consider it as a burdensome activity. According to Kuvaas (2006) and Rudman (2003), a performance appraisal and employee appraisal is a method by which the job performance of an employee is evaluated (generally in terms of quality, quantity, cost and time) typically by the immediate line manager or supervisor. Performance appraisal is a part of the process of guiding and managing career development in both private and public organizations. It involves the task of obtaining, analyzing and recording information about the relative worth of an employee to the organization. Mani (2002) states that performance appraisal is an analysis of an employee's recent successes and failures, personal strengths and weaknesses and suitability for promotion or further training. According to Rudman (2008), performance appraisal has a positive and negative impact. Employees who receive a good score on his/her appraisal are generally motivated to perform well and maintain his/her performance. Positive feedback on appraisals gives employee a feeling of worth and value, especially when accompanied by salary increases. If a supervisor gives an employee a poor score on his/her appraisal, the employee may feel a loss of motivation in the workplace and this can impact on the employee's performance.

The parameters, the characteristics and the standard for employee evaluation may be different, but the fundamentals of performance appraisal are the same. But performance appraisal is more effectively used as the tools of motivating and managing employee performance (Tassew, 2010). Performance appraisal involves two key players namely the raters and the ratees. In order to conduct a performance appraisal, both players need to refer to the organization's vision and mission. Management or the board of directors are responsible to supervise the whole process in general and is guided by other factors such as stakeholders and corporate governance of the organization. Subordinates play a role as raters, assessor or the evaluation officer. Their core business is to make an evaluation of the ratees' job performance. Subordinates are referred to the ratees whom their work performance will be evaluated. Occasionally, subordinates can play two roles at a time; they can be raters and, in another context, they can also be ratees. This shows that those who are in the higher post will evaluate ratees' work performance (Malik, Ahmad, Saof, & Safwan, 2010).

Employees' performance in the organization is a continuous process and need to be monitored on a timely basis. This is to ensure that improvements in performance are continuous and within time, the organization becomes a learning organization. Several important purposes of mentoring are to identify the gap that exists between existing employees (with abundance of experience) with new employees (with minimal experiences); to identify opportunities that can assist existing employees with unfamiliar task or challenges; to identify any problems in advance to achieve the existing standards; and to collect documentation data on the employee's performance for the final appraisal (Cook and Crossman, 2004). According to Stoner et al., (2011) performance appraisal compares individuals' job performance to standard developed for the individual's position and how it may prompt corrective action like additional training, a demotion or separation while high performance merits the word such as bonus or promotion. However, the condition under which work is performed should be such that enables employees to not only be economically highly productive and efficient, but happy people with proper developed skills.

2.2 Theoretical Review

Theories are formulated to explain, predict and help in understanding phenomenon. In many cases theories help to challenge or extend existing knowledge frontier within the limits of the critical bounding assumptions, (David, 2009). Accordingly, the relationship between human capital management and organizational performance can be explained by the following theories:

2.2.1 Resource Based View

The resource-based theory states that, the organizational resources and capabilities that are rare, valuable, non-substitutable, and imperfectly imitable form the basis for a firm's sustained competitive advantage. Resource based theory proposes that the firm can secure a sustained competitive advantage through facilitating the development of competencies that are embedded in a firm's human capital,

(Odhong *et al.* 2013). The theory recognizes human capital as the most valuable, non-substitutable and imperfectly imitable resource that a firm can successfully utilize to achieve organizational performance. Resource-based theory is linked to human capital theory in that, they both emphasize that investment in people adds to their value to the firm, (Baron and Armstrong 2012).

2.2.2 Human Capital Theory

The origin of human capital goes back to emergence of classical economics in 1776 and thereafter developed a scientific theory. The idea of investing in human capital was first developed by Adam Smith in 1776. He argued in his book the “Wealth of Nations” that there is a difference between education and acquiring skills. Economists such as Elliot (1991) developed the theory of human capital. He was concerned with human capital in terms of the quality, not quantity, of the labour supply. Human capital theory holds that it is the key competences, skills, knowledge and abilities of the employees that contribute to organization’s competitive advantage. The theory focuses attention on human resource training, development and as well as effective reward strategies and practices of an organization. According to the proponents of this theory, training as form of education is an investment that it can be potentially bestowed to employees for motivation and other social benefits. Human capital theorists believe that training as a form of education and earning power are correlated. Meaning the more trained one is, the more one can earn, and that the skills, knowledge and abilities that training provides can be transferred into the work in terms of performance and productivity (Dae-bong, 2009).

2.3 Empirical Review

Salako, Omotilewa and Sotunde (2014) investigated the human capital management situation in Nigeria, with a study of one-hundred employees of different commercial banks selected randomly in Abeokuta. Data were collected with a well-structured questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics. The findings of the study revealed that training which is one of the human capital management programs can improve employees’ performance. Happiness and Michael (2014) carried out a study on the impact of training and development on organizational performance: Evidence from selected Public Sector Organizations in Nigeria. The findings of the study revealed that, there is positive relationship between training/development and organizational performance. Odunayo, et al (2014) carried out a study on modelling the relationship between performance appraisal and organizational performance in Nigerian public sector, Lagos. The study utilized a survey design method with a structured questionnaire. The finding revealed that if managerial decisions are fair and just with equitable reward and promotion for job done, it will increase employees’ commitment and loyalty in the organization. Gunu, et al (2013) carried out a study on training and development as a tool for organizational performance: A study of selected banks in Nigeria. The findings of the study revealed that training and development have a significant impact on organizational performance. Olalere and Adenugba (2013) investigated human capital management in First Bank of Nigeria Plc with a study population of all categories of staff (Junior, Senior and Management staff) in the Seven (7) branches of First Bank of Nigeria Plc in Ibadan, Oyo State, using purposive sampling technique to select Seven (7) branches of First Bank in Ibadan metropolis and random sampling procedure to select the respondents in the branches. Both primary and secondary data were used, particularly questionnaire and in-depth interview as instruments for primary data collection. The findings of the study revealed that the human capital management has improved the skills, attitude and the performance of staff of the bank which invariably has led to the achievement of competitive advantage. Nadeem, et al (2013) conducted a study on the impact of performance appraisal on employee’s performance involving the Moderating Role of Motivation. They found that there is positive relationship between performance appraisal and employee’s performance.

Nzuve and Bundi (2012) conducted a study to determine the relationship between human capital management practices and performance of Commercial Banks in Kenya. The finding revealed that proper training and performance appraisal generally have a positive influence on organizational performance. Nzuve and Musyoka (2012) conducted a study on human capital management practices adopted by the National Social Security Fund. The finding revealed that NSF had implemented HCM practices but to a negligible extent. Nyong (2012) conducted a study on the performance of commercial banks in Nigeria. The study threw more light on the effect of managerial efficiency on the performance of commercial banks. The findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between human capital management and

organizational performance. Waseef and Iqbal (2011) conducted a study on the Impact of Human Capital Management on Organization. The population comprised 450 with sample size of 316. The findings of the study revealed that firm's human capital management has a significant positive impact on organizational performance. Idemobi and Onyeizugbe (2011) carried out a study on Performance Management as an imperative for effective performance in Delta State. The finding showed that performance review techniques have significant effect on employees' performance and that there is a significant relationship between performance incentives and employees' morale. According to Hewitt (2010), a research study conducted by CFO Research Services revealed that human capital issue is a key culprit in failed and subsequent financial woes. The results of the study revealed that human capital management should be offered a pride of place in an organization.

Bassi and McMurrer (2010) conducted a study on Human Capital and Organizational Performance: Next Generation Metrics as a Catalyst for change. The finding revealed that a core set of HCM drivers that could predict performance are leadership practices, employee engagement, knowledge accessibility, workforce optimization and learning capacity. Olufemi (2009) conducted a study on human capital development and organizational performance. The study found that firms' involvement in training and performance appraisal are found to correlate positively with organizational performance and its effectiveness. Muktar (2005) conducted a study on the impact of human capital development on the performance of commercial banks in Nigeria. He found that the performance of commercial banks is associated, to a great extent with the educational qualifications of its human resources. The study recommended that, if staff with experience could be complemented with those with higher qualifications, performance will undoubtedly improve.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study utilized survey research design. The choice of this research design was considered appropriate because it provided the researcher the opportunity of gathering data from a representative population of the study.

3.2 The Study Area

This study was conducted in United Bank for Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. The State is in the South-South zone of Nigeria with its capital at Uyo. The State is the largest oil producing state in Nigeria. The population of the State is estimated at about 309, 573 as of 2006 (NPC, 2006 report). It has a land area of 95km² (36. 7sq.ml), Wikipedia encyclopedia (2007). The people in the area are predominantly Ibibio; others include Annang, Oron, Eket, Obolo, Ibeno and other speaking tribes in Nigeria. Akwa Ibom State is inhabited by people of different walks of life such as teachers, businessmen, students, traders, civil servants and unemployed youths among others. The choice of this study area was driven by the relevance of the research topic.

3.3 Population of the Study

The population of the study consisted of 82 staff of United Bank for Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. The population distribution according to the branches is shown below:

Aka Road Branch	24 (4 senior staff, 4 management staff and 16 junior staff).
Abak Road Branch	22 (3 senior staff, 3 management staff and 16 junior staff).
Nwaniba Road Branch	18 (4 senior staff, 1 management staff and 13 junior staff).
Udoudoma Branch	18 (3 senior staff, 3management staff and 12 junior staff).
TOTAL	82

3.4 Sample Size and Sampling Technique

As a result of the inability of the researcher to effectively study the whole staff strength, 68 was used as sample size population using Taro Yamen scientific technique:

$$n = \frac{82}{1 + 82(0.5)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{82}{1 + 82(0.0025)} \\
 &= \frac{82}{1 + 0.205} \\
 &= \frac{82}{1.205} \\
 n &= 68
 \end{aligned}$$

3.5 Sources of Data Collection

Data were collected from primary and secondary sources. Primary data were obtained through questionnaire and personal interviews with the staff of the bank. This method was adopted to enable detailed and independent information not covered by the questionnaire to be expressed by the respondents. Secondary data were obtained from published reports, books, internet, journals, newspapers and magazines.

3.6 Instrument for Data Collection

Data were collected through questionnaire titled “Human Capital Management and Organizational Performance Questionnaire (HCMOPQ)” carefully designed and administered to the respondents, as well as through personal interviews. Questionnaire was used as the main instrument for data collection. Section A of the questionnaire contained personal information of the respondents. Section B contained fifteen (15) close ended questions using a four-point scale instrument through which the opinions of the respondents were expressed.

3.7 Validity of Research Instrument

The validity of the research instrument was assessed by the research’s supervisor and other research experts in the Faculty of Business Administration and lecturers in the Departments of English, Measurement and Evaluation all in the University of Uyo. These experts assessed the relevance of each item in relation to the objectives of the study, the hypotheses to be tested and language used in developing the items as well as the comprehensibility of each item in relation to the cognitive level of the respondents. They validated the instrument by effecting necessary corrections, examining the contents and ascertaining clarification of ideas as well as appropriateness of the items. The final instrument is reflected on the appendix.

3.8 Reliability of the Instrument

In order to determine the reliability of the instrument used in the study, the corrected questionnaire was administered randomly on selected staff of the First Bank Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. This approach was repeated with the same group after one-month period and the results obtained from the first and second pre-test were consistent, therefore, the instrument is reliable.

3.9 Administration of the Instrument

The exercise was done with the help of operations managers of each branch. This enhanced return rate of above 80%. Questionnaires.

3.10 Method of Data Analysis

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient (PPMC) statistical method was used to test the hypotheses.

4. DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 Analysis of Respondents’ Socio-demographic Information

Data on Table 4.1 shows the frequency distribution of respondents’ socio-demographic background. As indicated, Table 4.1 shows that the total number of respondents was 56 constituting 48.2% male and 51.8% female. The views being expressed in this study are representative of both male and female respondents but with female respondents the majority. In terms of age distribution of the respondents, 25.0% were less than 30 years, 42.9% were between 30-40years, 28.6% were between 41-50 years of age, and 3.5% were above age 50. Thus, most of the respondents were between 30-40 years old. In addition, Table 4.1 also reveals that 26.7% respondents have less than 5 years of working experience, 25.6% respondents

have worked between 6-10years, 30.2% respondents. From this result, it can be inferred that majority of respondents have over five years working experience with their organization. Among the respondents, 34.9% were single and 65.1% were married. On the basis of highest educational qualification, respondents consist of 10.7% SSCE/WASC certificate holders, 32.1% OND/NCE diploma certificate holders, 39.3% HND/B.Sc/B.A graduates, and 17.9% were master's degree holders. This simply suggests that most respondents were well educated to understand the issues at stake and to contribute accordingly.

Table 4.1: Respondents' Socio-Demographic Profile (N= 56)

Demographic Distribution	Variable	Frequency	Percentage %
Gender	Male	27	48.2
	Female	29	51.8
Age of Respondent	Less than 30years	14	25.0
	31-40years	24	42.9
	41-50years	16	28.6
	Over 50 years	2	3.5
Working Experience	1-5years	15	26.7
	6-10 years	14	25.0
	10-15 years	16	30.2
	16 years and above	11	17.4
Highest Qualification	SSCE/WAEC	6	10.7
	OND/NCE	18	32.1
	HND/B.SC/B.A	22	39.3
	M.SC/MBA	10	17.9
Marital Status	Married	31	36.0
	Single	25	64.0

Source: Field Survey, 2023

4.2 Descriptive Analysis of Research Questions

The data analysis in this section is presented on the basis of the research questions.

Mean and Standard Deviation (SD) are the main descriptive statistical tools used for the analysis. The mean value of 3.0 is used in taking decision. This is derived by dividing the sum of the scale by 5. Thus, any item with a mean value of 3.0 and above is taken as an acceptable index of agreement while a mean score below 3.0 was taken as an index of disagreement.

Research Questions 1 – What has been the relationship between staff training and organizational performance in United Bank for Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State?

Table 4.2: Mean and standard deviation on the relationship between staff training and organizational performance (N=56)

Response construct	Mean	SD	Remark
Staff training is one of the core policies issues in my organization	4.08	0.89	Agree
Training in my organization aims at improving employee's job knowledge and skills required to perform their jobs.	4.23	0.98	Agree
There is in-service training or on-the-job-training in my organization.	4.15	0.94	Agree
Training in my organization can be said to be effective.	2.68	1.18	Disagree
Training in my organization is not lopsided.	2.29	1.31	Disagree

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.2 shows the mean and standard deviation of responses on the relationship between staff training and organizational performance. It can be observed that three out of the five constructs had their

mean value above the 3.0 benchmark used for decision. For instance, the statement “Training in your organization aims at improving employee’s job knowledge and skills required to perform their jobs” (Mean= 4.23, SD=0.98) had the highest mean value. Participants were also of the opinion that training is one of the core policy issue in their bank (Mean= 4.23, SD=0.98), and that in-service training is a common practice in the bank (Mean= 4.15, SD=0.94). Though most respondents agreed that training is given priority in their organization, they however, disagreed (Mean=2.68, SD=1.18) that training is effective to the extent of producing positive results due probably to its lopsidedness (Mean=2.29, SD=1.31).

Research Questions 2 – What is the relationship between staff performance appraisal and organizational performance in United Bank for Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State?

Table 4.3: Mean and standard deviation on the relationship between staff performance appraisal and organizational performance (N=56)

Response constructs	Mean	SD	Remark
Staff in my organization are adequately appraised to understand their weaknesses and strengths on the job.	3.23	1.26	Agree
Timely appraisal of staff gives room for redesigning of staff training programs.	3.83	0.23	Agree
Staff performance appraisal has a positive impact on my organization.	3.25	1.47	Agree
Staff performance appraisal system in my organization is objective.	4.63	0.37	Agree

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Results on Table 4.3 reveals that organizational performance could just depend on effective performance appraisal. Respondents were strongly of the opinion that by being objective in evaluation (Mean= 4.63; SD=0.37), performance appraisal helps management and staff understand their weaknesses and strengths on the job (Mean= 3.23; SD=1.26), and therefore gives room for redesigning relevant staff training programs (Mean= 3.83; SD=0.23) which is capable of making lasting and positive impact on overall performance of the Bank (Mean= 3.25; SD=1.47). This result is an indication that human capital development can be achieved by bank management through effective implementation of performance appraisal.

Research Questions 3- What is the relationship between the joint influence of staff training and staff performance appraisal on the performance of United Bank for Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom state?

Staff training and appraisal of work performance are two key human capital management functions with capability to influence organizational performance. Given this understanding, it is expected that effective execution of these two functions would result in significant outcomes to the organization under study. Therefore, respondents were asked to indicate how the joint use of training and performance appraisal has over time affected overall performance of the bank. Their responses are as summarized on Table 4.4 below.

Table 4.4: Mean and standard deviation on relationship between staff training and staff performance appraisal on the performance (N=56)

Response constructs	Mean	SD	Remark
My bank is very profitable.	4.26	0.87	Agree
The rate of employee turnover in my bank is low.	3.66	1.04	Agree
My bank recently has won a recognition for outstanding performance from Central Bank.	3.64	1.06	Agree
My bank is known to be responsive to CBN regulations.	3.78	1.12	Agree

Source: Field Survey, 2023

On Table 4.4, it is clear that the joint application of training and appraisal enhances profitability (Mean= 4.26; SD=0.87), reduced staff turnover (Mean= 3.66; SD=1.04), improves the bank's image and position in the industry through recognition by CBN (Mean= 3.64; SD=1.06), and helps the bank to be responsive to CBN regulations (Mean= 3.78; SD=1.12). Thus, from aggregate of responses shown on Table 4.4, it can be inferred that the bank's performance has been enhanced through effective management of human capital.

4.3 Test of hypotheses

Hypothesis One

Staff training has no significant relationship with organizational performance in United Bank for Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Correlation between staff training and performance was tested using the Pearson product moment correlation technique and the results are as summarized on Table 4.5

Table 4.5 Pearson's correlation matrix showing relationship between staff training and organizational performance

		Staff Training	Organizational Performance
Staff Training	Pearson Correlation	1	.356**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	56	56
Organizational Performance	Pearson Correlation	.356**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	56	56

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

It can be observed from Table 4.5 that relationship between staff training and organizational performance is positive and significant at 0.01 level ($r = 0.356$, $p < 0.01$). This suggests that organization performance is dependent on the extent of its staff training. This implies that increased investment in staff training by the bank would yield greater returns in organizational performance. Thus, a percentage increase/decrease in training as human capital management element will lead to a proportional (35.6%) increase/decrease in bank performance in terms of increased profitability, reduced staff turnover rate, enhanced public image for the bank, and greater responsiveness to CBN regulations.

Hypothesis Two

Staff performance appraisal has no significant relationship with organizational performance in United Bank for Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4.6: Correlation between performance appraisal and organizational performance

		Performance Appraisal	Organizational Performance
Performance Appraisal	Pearson Correlation	1	.495**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	56	56
Organizational Performance	Pearson Correlation	.495**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	56	56

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

On Table 4.6, Result shows that relationship between performance appraisal and organizational performance is positive and significant at 0.01 probability level ($r = 0.495$, $p < 0.01$). The inference is therefore drawn that relationship exists between performance appraisal and organizational performance. The correlation coefficient ($r = 0.495$) shown on Table 4.6 implies that 49.5% increase in bank performance can be achieved as the bank becomes more objective in evaluating employee performance.

4.4 Discussion of Findings

The main aim of this study was to examine the relationship between human capital management and organizational performance in United Bank for Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. This section is concerned with the discussion of findings that emerged from the result of data analysis. They are discussed under specific objectives of the study.

4.4.1 Staff training and Organizational Performance in United Bank for Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

The first objective was to examine the relationship between staff training and organizational performance in United Bank for Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Pearson correlation analysis was performed with a view towards achieving the above objective. It was found that significant positive relationship exists between the staff training and organizational performance in United Bank for Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State as depicted by the following results ($r = 0.356$, $p < 0.01$). This suggests that organizational performance is dependent on the extent of its staff training. This implies that increased investment in staff training by the bank would yield greater returns in organizational performance. Thus, a percentage increase/decrease in training as human capital management element will lead to a proportional (35.6%) increase/decrease in bank performance in terms of increased profitability, reduced staff turnover rate, enhanced public image for the bank, and greater responsiveness to CBN regulations. This finding is consistent with Gunu, et al (2013) where relationship between staff training and organizational performance was reported to have significant impact on organizational performance of banks in Nigeria. The finding is also in line with Waseef and Iqbal (2011) which found that firm's human capital management has a significant positive impact on organizational performance. This finding also corroborates with that of Muhammad (2012) who opined that training has a positive significant impact in improving employee's understanding and their specific skills of enhancing organizational performance.

4.4.2 Staff Performance Appraisal and Organizational Performance in United Bank for Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

The second objective attempted to examine whether significant relationship exists between staff performance appraisal and organizational performance in United Bank for Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Based on the study, it was found that positive relationship exists between staff performance appraisal and organizational performance in United Bank for Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State in terms of the following indicators ($r = 0.495$, $p < 0.01$). However, the inference is therefore drawn that relationship exists between performance appraisal and organizational performance. The correlation coefficient ($r = 0.495$) shown on Table 4.6 implies that 49.5% increase in bank performance can be achieved as the bank becomes more objective in evaluating employee performance. This finding is in line with Nadeem, et al (2013) that there is positive relationship between performance appraisal and employee's performance. They discovered that motivation as a moderator positively affected the relationship between performance appraisal and employee's performance. The finding is also consistent with that of Nzuve and Bundi (2012) who found that performance appraisal generally has a positive influence on organizational performance as measured by both turnover growth and return on assets. Similarly, the finding is in support of Olufemi (2009) that firms' involvement in performance appraisal is found to correlate positively with employees' performance and its effectiveness in an organization.

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of the Findings

This research was designed to examine the relationship between human capital management and organizational performance in United Bank for Africa Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. To achieve this objective, survey research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study consisted of management staff, senior staff and junior staff of the United Bank for Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State which is made up of 82 staff with sample size of 68 staff. The study utilized Taro Yamane scientific technique. The instrument used for data collection was Human Capital Management and Organizational Performance Questionnaire (HCMOPQ). Tables, Mean, Standard Deviation and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient were adopted as analytical tools for this study. Two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The result of the study showed that there was a positive significant relationship between human capital management and organizational performance in United Bank for Africa Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. The result of the findings also revealed that organizational performance is dependent on the extent of its staff training and timely appraisal of employees. This implies that increased investment in staff training and timely appraisal of employees by the bank would yield greater returns in organizational performance.

5.2 Conclusion

In conclusion, there is a positive significant relationship between human capital management and organizational performance in United Bank for Africa Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. The independent variables namely; staff training and staff performance appraisal contribute significantly positive to organizational performance. The finding revealed that organizational performance is dependent on the extent of its staff training and performance appraisal which implies that increased investment in staff training and performance appraisal by the bank would yield greater returns in organizational performance. From the findings of this study, it could be concluded that the inability of most organizations, particularly banks to achieve their performance or objectives may be attributed to external or exogenous factors which are outside the control of the organizations.

5.3 Recommendations

From the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Organizations particularly, United Bank for Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State should be more proactive in human capital management programs to ensure effective and improved performance of both the employees and the organization.
- ii. The close system method of performance appraisal should be discouraged; the employees should be openly appraised and rewarded to ensure fairness and transparency.

References

- Atif, A. N., Ijaz, R. and Nadeem, S. (2011). Employee retention relationship to training and development: A compensation perspective. *African Journal of Business Management* Vol.5 (7), pp. 2679-2685.
- Armstrong, M. (2012). *Strategic Human Resources Management: A guide to action*. 3rd edition. Thompson-Shore, Inc.
- Armstrong, M. (2010), *A handbook of Human Resource Management Practice*. (11th ed.), London: Kogan Page Limited.
- Armstrong, M. (2009). *Armstrong's Handbook of Human Resource Management Practice*, 11th edn. London: Kogan Page Ltd.
- Bailey, T. (1993). 'Organizational Innovation in the Apparel Industry'. *Industrial Relations*, 32, 30-48.
- Barney, J. B. (1991). "Firm's Resources and Sustained Competitive Advantage", *Journal of Management*, vol. 17, pp. 99-120.
- Bakare, K. O. (2012). Training needs of hotel employees as correlate of job satisfaction in Ile -Ife, Osun State. *JABU international journal of social and management sciences*. 4(1), 17-24.
- Baron, A. and Armstrong, M. (2012). *Human Capital Management: Achieving Added Value through People*, London and Philadelphia, Kogan Page Publishers.

- Bassi, L. and McMurrer, D. (2010). Human Capital and Organizational Performance: Next Generation Metrics as a Catalyst for Change, USA, Whitepaper, McBassi & Company. Inc.
- Bontis, N. (2009), "Management organizational knowledge by diagnosing intellectual capital: framing and advancing the state of the field", *International Journal of Technology Management*, Vol. 18 Nos. 5-8, pp. 433-62.
- Bontis, N. (2008), "Assessing Knowledge assets: a review of the models used to measure intellectual capital", *International Journal of Management Reviews*, Vol. 3 No. 1, pp. 41-60.
- Bontis, N. Crossan, M. and Hulland, J. (2008), "Managing an organizational learning system by aligning stocks and flows", *Journal of Management Studies*, Vol. 39 No. 4, pp. 437-690.
- Bontis, N., Keow. C. C. W. and Richardson, S. (2000), Intellectual capital and business performance in Malaysian industries, *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 1 (1), 85-100.
- Boxall, P. (1998) Achieving competitive advantage through human resource strategy: Towards a theory of industry dynamics, *Human Resources Management Review* 8 (3), 268-288.
- Brown, D. (2010) Performance Management: can the practice ever deliver the policy; Brighton: Institute for Employment Studies.
- Comma, M. R. (2008), *Effect of Manpower Training and Development on Staff Performance and Retention in Federal College of Education, Zaria*. Being A Thesis Submitted to the Postgraduate school in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Award of the Degree of Master of Public Administration.
- Cook, J. and Crossman A. (2004) "Satisfaction with performance appraisal systems: A study of role perceptions" *Journal of Managerial Psychology*. Vol. 19 (5), pp. 526 – 541.
- Cuming, M. W (1975). *The Theory and Practice of Personnel Management*. London: Heinemann.
- Dae-bong, K. (2009). *Human Capital and its Measurement*, the 3rd OECD World Forum on "Statistics, Knowledge and Policy", Charting progress, Building Visions, Improving life, Busan Korea 27 – 30 October. Viewed on <http://www.oecd.worldforum2009.org>.
- Davenport, T. H. and Prusac, L. (2010), *Working Knowledge: How Organizations Manage What They Know*. Boston, MA: Harvard Business School Press.
- David, F. A. (2009) *Statistical models: Theory and practice* (revised ed.), UK Cambridge University Press.
- Delery, J., & Shaw, J. (2001). 'The Strategic Management of People in Work Organizations. Review, Synthesis, and extension, in (ed.). *Research in Personnel and Human Resource Management* (Research in Personnel and Human Resource Management, Volume 20). Emerald Group Publishing Limited, pp. 165-197.
- Devi, V. R. and Shaik, N. (2012), "Training and Development – A Jump Starter for Employee Performance and Organizational Effectiveness." *International Journal of Social Science and Interdisciplinary Research*, 1 (7) July, pp2277-3630.
- Drucker, J., White, G., Hegewisch, A., Mayne, L. (1996) 'Between hard and soft HRM: human resource management in the construction industry: *Construction Management and Economics*, 14, 405-416.
- Drucker, P. F (1999). *Knowledge-worker Productivity: The Biggest Challenge*. California management Review, Vol. 41(2)
- Dyer, L., & Reeves, T. (1995). HR strategies and firm performance: what do we know and where do we need to go *International Journal of Human Resource Management* 6:3, 656-670.
- Edvinsson, L. and Malone, M. S. (1997), *Intellectual Capital: Realizing Your Company's True Value by Finding Its Hidden Brain Power*. New York: Harper Business, NY.
- Ezeani, N.E. and Oladele, R. (2013), "Implications of Training and Development Programs on Accountants Productivity in Selected Business Organizations in Onitsha, Anambra State, Nigeria", *International Journal of Asian Social Science*, 3(1) pp 266-281.
- Guest, D. E. (2011). Human resource management and performance still searching for some answers. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 21 (1), 3-13.
- Gunu,U., Oni, E., Tsado, E. & Ajayi, O. (2013). Training and Development as a tool for Organizational Performance: Case study of Selected Banks in Nigeria. *Kuwait Chapter of Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*. Vol. 2, No. 10.

- Happiness Ozioma Obi-Anike and Michael Chidiebere Ekwe (2014) Impact of Training and Development on Organizational Effectiveness: Evidence from Selected Public Sector Organizations in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management*. ISSN 2222-1905 (Paper) ISSN 2222-2839 (Online).
- Hassen, R. (1995), "Factors correlated with trainees' turn over and human capital investment: suggested model and applied study", PhD dissertation, Faculty of commerce, Alexandria University, Alexandria (in Arabic).
- Herzberg, F. (1998). *Work and nature of man*. London. Uk: Crosby.
<http://www.econlib.org/library/Enc/HumanCapital.html>. Retrieved on 15/7/2011.
- Hewitt, A. (2010). *Human Capital Management and the Success or failure of M &A*, Research Report, CFO Research Service, www.cfo.com viewed on 13/5/2014.
- Holbeche, L. (2004). *Aligning Human resources and Business Strategy*, Oxford: Elsevier Butterworth-Heinemann.
- Huselid, M. (1995). 'The Impact of Human Resource Management Practices on Turnover, Productivity and Corporate Financial Performances, *Academy of Management Journal* 38, 635-672.
- Idemobi, Ellis I. and Onyeizugbe, C. (2011). Performance Management as an Imperative for effective Performance in Delta State owned Organizations. *Sacha Journal of Policy and Strategic Studies*, Volume 1, Number 2, pp 46-54.
- Inyang, B. J. and Akpama, A. M. (2002), *Personnel Management Practice in Nigeria*. Calabar: Merb Business Centre.
- Irene, F. L. (2013), "The Impact of Training and Development on Worker Performance and Productivity in Public Sector Organizations", *A Case Study of Ghana Ports and Harbours Authority*. A Thesis submitted to the Institute of Distance Learning, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science & Technology, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of COMMONWEALTH EXECUTIVE MASTERS OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION Institute of Distance Learning-KNUST.
- Irene, F.L. (2009). A Thesis on the Impact of Training and Development on the Worker Performance and Productivity in the Public Sector Organizations: A case study of Ghana Ports and Harbours Authority (Submitted Thesis), *Institute of Distance Learning: KNUST*
- Johnson, D. L. (2002), Knowledge, innovation and share value, *International Journal of Management Reviews* 4(2), 101-134.
- Jones, G. R., George, J. M., Hill, C. W. L. (2000) *Contemporary Management* New York, Irwin and McGraw Hills.
- Kearns, P. (2009). *Evaluating the ROI from Learning*. London, CIPD.
- Khandekar, A. and Sharma, A. (2003) Managing human resource capabilities for sustainable competitive advantage: An empirical analysis from Indian global organization, *Education and Training*, 47 (8/9), 628-639.
- Kochan, T. & Osterman, P. (1994). *The mutual gains enterprise: forgiving a winning partnership among labor, management and government*. Boston mass: Harvard business school press.
- Koontz, H. O. C. and Weihrich, H. (1980). *Management*, 7th ed., New York McGraw-Hill.
- Kuvaas, B. (2006). Performance Appraisal Satisfaction and Employee outcomes; mediating and moderating roles of work motivation. *International Journal of Human Resources Management*. 17(3): 504-522.
- Lawler, E. (1992). *The Ultimate Advantage: Creating the High Involvement Organization*. San Francisco: McGraw Hill International Press.
- Levine, D. (1995). *Reinventing the Work place: How Business and Employees Can Both Win*. Washington DC: Brookings institution.
- Mackey, K. & Johnson, G. (2000). *The Strategic Management of Human Resources in New Zealand*. Auckland: Irwin/McGraw-Hill.
- Malik, etal (2010) Relationship of Organizational Commitment, job satisfaction and Layoff survivors Productivity. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 2 (7): 200-210.
- Mani, B. (2002). Performance appraisal systems, productivity, and motivation: A case study. *Public Personnel Management*. 31(19): 141-159.

- Marimuthu, M. et al (2009) "Human Capital Development and Its Impact on Firm's Performance: Evidence from Developmental Economics", in the *Journal of International Social Research*, 2/8 summer, ismail. Pdf. Retrieved on 15/7/2011.
- Meysam F, Mohammad R J, Behrooz D, Ebrahim D. (2012). The Effect of Performance Appraisal Satisfaction on Employee's Outputs Implying on the Moderating Role of Motivation in Workplace. *International Journal of Business and Management Tomorrow* vol.2, Number 4.
- Miller, P. (1989). Strategic HRM: what it is and it isn't, *Personnel Management* 46-51.
- Muhammad, S.K (2012). Examining effect of training on job satisfaction of NGO sector employees in Islamabad. Master of Science thesis of Mohammad Ali Jinnah University, Islamabad.
- Nadeem, I., Naveed, A., Zeeshan, H., Yumna, B. & Qura-ul-ain (2013). Impact of performance appraisal on employee's performance involving the Moderating Role of Motivation. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review (OMAN chapter)* Vol. 3, No. 1.
- Nyong, M. (2012) Monetary Policy and Banks Performance in Nigeria. *CBN Econ. Finance. Rev.* 34 (3).
- Nzuve S. and Musyoka A. (2012). *Human Capital Management Practices Adopted by the National Social Security Fund*, Research Journal of Multidisciplinary Social Sciences (RJOMSS), Vol. 1, issue, Nairobi, Kenya.
- Nzuve, S. and Bundi, E. G. (2012). *Human Capital Practices and Firms Performance: A Survey of Commercial Banks in Kenya*, Social Science Research Network, Nairobi, Kenya.
- Obikoya, J. (2003) *Human Resource Management*. 1st edition. Ogun: Verbic Publications.
- Odhong E. A. and Were S. (2013). "Human Capital Management as a tool for value creation", in proceedings of First SHRD Annual Research Conference, 12th and 13th September, Nairobi, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology main campus.
- Odunayo, P. S, Olumuyiwa, F. O, Oyinlola, C. O & James, O. A (2014). Modelling the Relationship between Performance Appraisal and Organizational Productivity in Nigerian Public Sector. *Journal of Economic Management Innovation (EMI)* vol. 6. Issue 2. ISSN: 1804-1299 (print) 1805-353 (online).
- Okanya, P. S. (2008). Reconciling organizational performance and employee satisfaction through training: the case of soroti district local government. (Unpublished) M A. Thesis, Graduate School of Development Studies: p. 66.
- Olalere, T. O. and Adenugba, A. A. (2013). "Human Capital Development in First Bank of Nigeria Plc". *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 4 (2), 783-801.
- Olufemi, A. J. (2009). Human Capital Development Practices and Organizational Effectiveness: *A focus on the contemporary Nigerian Banking Industry*, *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences* Vol. 6 No. p. 194-199.
- Olusanya, S. O., Awotungase, S. A. and Ohadebere, E. C. (2012), "Training and Development, A Vital Tool for Organizational Effectiveness", *Journal of Business and Management* 2278-487X. Vol 6(2) Nov-Dec. PP 48-57.
- Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) (2011).
- Purcell, J. (2010). Best Practice or best fit: Chimera or Cul-de-sac. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 9(3): 26-41.
- Qureshi M, Tahir Hijazi T, Syed Ramey I, Mohammad (2007). Impact of Human Resource Management Practices on Pakistani organizations. *J. Bus. Policy. Res.* 3(2): 128-138.
- Raja, A. G. K., Furqan, A. K. and Muhammad, A. K. (2011). Impact of Training and Development on Organizational Performance. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*. 11(7).
- Robbins, S. P. (1982). *Personnel: The Management of Human Resources*, 2nd Ed, New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- Roberts B. (2020). *The Challenges And Value of Human Resource Planning*. www.work911.com/planningmaster/Human_Resource_Planning/ Retrieved on 20th September, 2020.
- Rudman, R. (2008). *Human Resources Management in New Zealand*. Auckland: Pearson Education New Zealand Limited.
- Salako, M. A., Omotilewa, O. O. and Sotunde, T. (Online). Human Resources Development in Nigerian Commercial Banks: An Empirical. International Conference for Future Education. Available at:

http://conference.pixelonline.net/edu_future/common/download/paper_pdf/SOE62-Salako.pdf.

Retrieved 15th April, 2014.

- Sajuyigbe, A.S and Amusat, (2012). Staff training and development as managerial tools for organizational effectiveness: An appraisal of First bank. *JABU international journal of social and management sciences*. 4(1), 100-109.
- Schultz, T. W. (1981) Investing in people, the Economics of Population Quarterly, Berkley: University of California Press.
- Schultz, W.T. (1971) Investment in human capital: The role of Education and Research: London. The Free Press New York, Collier Macmillin Ltd.
- Shubin, J. A. (1957). Business Management: An Introduction to Business and Industry. London: banes and Noble Books.
- Stoner, J., Freeman, R. & Gilbert, D. (2011). Management. (6th Ed.) New Delhi: Prentice Hall. Studies, Vol. 29, pp. 713-40.
- Tassew, S. G. (2010). Performance Appraisal and its Significance as a Human Resource Management Tool. Proceedings of May 2010 *Global Awareness Society International*.
- Tyson, S. (1997). Human Resource Strategy: A process for managing the contribution of HRM to Organizational Performance. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 11 (3): 1029-48.
- Ubeku, A. K. (1975). Personnel Management in Nigeria. Benin: Ethiope Publishing Corporation.
- Vichet, S. (nd). A Framework for Managing Training Programs to Enhance Organizational Operation Performance. Southern Illinois University Carbondale. Retrieved on 12/12/12 from <http://wed.siu.edu/Journal/vo III num3/article%205.pdf>.
- Waetherly, A. L. (2003). The value of people: The challenges and opportunities of human capital measurement and reporting, Research quarterly, *Society for Human Resource Management*.
- Waseef Jamal and M. Iqbal Saif (2011). Impact of Human Capital Management on Organizational Performance. *European Journal of Economics, Finance and Administrative Sciences*. ISSN 1450-2275 Issue 34 (2011).
- World Bank (1995). Monitoring Environmental Progress. Washington, D. C.
- Wurim, B. P (2012) Human Capital Planning and Organizational Performance in the Nigerian Public Sector. *Journal of Research in Arts & Social Sciences*. Vol 1 No1.